

Documents Laid Open Data 1922-2019

This document describes the metadata fields for a published dataset of the ‘Documents Laid’ collection at Ireland’s Oireachtas Library (<https://zenodo.org/record/3991538#.X2s5mOSP6Uk>). It is intended to assist researchers with analysis of the dataset.

Fields	Description
Title	The title of the document, taken from the cover page or first page, in line with Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules. Sometimes titles are improvised if there is no title on the front page of a document. There are also some standardised titles, e.g. for special adviser contracts.
Author	Entries are drawn from a controlled vocabulary in the Library of Congress Name Authority Headings or are local headings formatted in a similar way. This is used to record the names of individual authors of a document. For committee reports, the chair of the committee is often recorded as the author.
Corporate Author	Library of Congress Name Authority Headings or formatted in the same way. This is a controlled entry field, used to record the names of an organisation, department, agency or committee that authored the document.
Place	Place of publication – usually the head office of the corporate body or agency responsible for the document. Most often taken from printed details on the publication itself. In some older records, if the place was unknown, the Latin abbreviation for ‘sine loco’ was used, e.g. [s.l.]
Approx Place	New column derived from the Place field. Most often taken from printed details on the publication itself. As per traditional library cataloguing rules, if a place was not printed on the document but was assumed, it was recorded in the Place field with square brackets. These approximate values were transferred to this newly created column.

Description	Page numbers, illustrations, measurement of the physical version of the document.
Publication Date	Unless otherwise indicated on the document, this is generally taken as the year the document has been laid. Inconsistencies between this date and the date laid may be explained by a delay in laying a particular document, e.g. a treaty published in the early twentieth century may not have been laid until decades later.
Approx Publication Date	New column derived from the Publication Date field. As per traditional library cataloguing rules, if a date was not printed on the document but was assumed, it was recorded in the Publication Date field with square brackets. These approximate values were transferred to this newly created column.
Publisher	The name of the publisher, most often taken from printed details on the publication itself.
Other Title	Used for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional portions of a title that is too long for the main Title field (as is often the case for many European Commission proposal (COM) documents) • The Irish version of a title • Statutory instrument numbers, e.g. "S.I. no. 12 of 2018" • Commission proposal (COM) numbers, i.e. "COM (2017) 43"
Subjects	Entries are drawn from the controlled vocabulary list of the Library of Congress Subject Authority Headings , or formatted in the same way. These are not used for Statutory Instruments or Commission proposal documents, so there are many missing values. Many of the recent Documents Laid have 'DL' (meaning 'document laid') as a subject, generated automatically by the system at the point of laying.
Control number	A local reference number for the document. Several numbering systems have been in place over the years, including 'Prn'. More recent documents have been given a running 'DL' number by administrators in the Oireachtas Library.
Notes	A free-text field, containing information about the DL number and any other relevant information about the document, including if the document was laid with errors previously.
Subcollection	This has traditionally been used for a small number of documents only, particularly Statutory Instruments and Committee Reports.

Language	Used only for non-English documents.
Laid Before	This denotes the House/s before which the document was laid. Most documents are laid before both the Dáil and Seanad.
Originating Authority	This field is currently used to record the committee, department or agency laying the document, including the department who is laying on behalf of an agency under its authority. For example, the Department of Education lays the annual report of the Teaching Council, so the Originating Authority is the Department of Education, and the Teaching Council is recorded as the Corporate Author. On multiple occasions, however, this field was used to describe the author rather than the department.
Legislation	The section of the legislation that states the document must be laid before the Houses. Many sections of the Acts are incorrect, as this entry was often interpreted as the section of the legislation related to the creation of a document rather than the command to lay it. If the document is laid for information only, the field contains "N/A"
Date Laid	The date the document was laid before the Houses.
Year Laid	New column derived from the date laid field, containing the year only. This is a more representative date field than the publication date.
Motion of Approval	This field denotes whether there a motion of approval required by the document. It refers primarily to Statutory Instruments, e.g. a draft statutory instrument may require a motion of approval from the Dáil. This field could be incorrect for some historical documents, as the question was not always understood by those laying the documents.
Statutory Period	This field denotes whether there is a period of parliamentary sitting days within which the document can be annulled. It refers primarily to statutory instruments, e.g. under some laws an order or regulation can be annulled in the House within 21 sitting days. There are many incorrect and missing entries in this field, as documents were often laid without any knowledge of this legislative requirement.
Dáil Order Paper	The number and date of the Dáil Order Paper on which the title of the document appeared. This is manually entered and may contain inconsistencies.

Dáil Order Paper Date	A new column derived from the Dáil Order Paper field, containing the year only.
Seanad Order Paper	The number and date of the Seanad Order Paper on which the title of the document appeared. This is manually entered and may contain inconsistencies. Due to requirements set by the Seanad office, not all titles appear on the Seanad Order Paper.
Seanad Order Paper Date	A new column derived from the Seanad Order Paper field, containing the year only.

For more information please contact library.and.research@oireachtas.ie